

A case study of hotels' perceptions of online self-audit tools, as well as the obstacles and motivating factors for investment technologies that are green and energy efficient

Wendell L. Galapate*, Melbert V. Animas, Jennefer Y. Yap

School of International Hospitality and Tourism Management, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding author: wlgalapate@sdca.edu.ph

Abstract

As a result of its energy consumption, the hospitality industry contributes significantly to global carbon dioxide emissions. It was decided to conduct a cross-sectional study of 40 hotel general managers in Philippines, Germany, Singapore, and Switzerland in order to find out what the barriers and motivators are for making sustainability investments and using online self-audit tools. The response rate was 8.8 percent, which was satisfactory. Despite the widespread use of government-sponsored incentives, financial constraints and profit-driven pressures continue to be the primary impediments to long-term sustainability investments. The potential cost savings associated with environmental impact mitigation, on the other hand, serve as the most powerful motivator for many. When it comes to making sustainable investments, energy efficiency has emerged as the ultimate goal for hoteliers to strive for. It has also emerged as a critical factor when using online self-audit tools, as a result of rising energy costs.

Keywords: Impacts on the environment; online audits; obstacles; drivers of change.

To cite this article:

Galapate, W. L., Animas, M. V., & Yap, J. Y. (2021). A case study of hotels' perceptions of online self-audit tools, as well as the obstacles and motivating factors for investment technologies that are green and energy efficient. *Hospitalite*, 5, 23-31.

Introduction

Global carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions are attributed to tourism as a whole, with an average share of 5% (Pratt et al., 2011). Hotels are estimated to account for 20% of total tourism industry emissions, or 1% of total CO₂ emissions (Pratt et al., 2011). The extensive use of water and the generation of both solid and liquid wastes are well-known features of the hospitality industry (Chen et al., 2010). Turning the operations around and looking for ways to: (1) technologies that are energy efficient should be implemented; and (2) increased reliance on clean, renewable energy sources, was recognized by some hospitality industry leaders and managers. More than a quarter of a century ago, studies revealed that hoteliers faced significant obstacles to making sustainability investments, including high initial investment costs and a lack of familiarity with concerns about the environment (Post & Altman, 1994).

A decade ago, a study of the hospitality sector revealed that hoteliers were skeptical of the possibility of increased revenue growth as a result of environmental management system implementation. In this instance, it appears as though the perceived high cost of mitigating environmental impacts serves as a deterrent to the implementation of environmental management systems (Darnall & Edwards, 2006). Since there has been a sustained public interest in environmental issues, and because there are numerous incentive programs in place, there has been some debate about whether both impediments and motivators for making Environmental mitigation investments are made to reduce environmental impacts have changed over time. What, then, can be done in this particular situation to turn words into actions?

The objectives of this study are the following: (1) to compare the motivations and barriers for investing in green technologies in the literature to those collected through primary research; and (2) to develop a set of recommendations based on the findings of an investigation into hoteliers' perceptions of online self-help tools on the potential for online self-help tools to act as a guide for improvement toward mitigating climate change.

Barriers and Motivating Factors for Sustainability Investment

Environmental adoption is hindered by both industrial and organizational barriers, which Post and Altman (1994) categorized into two groups. For example, the activities of a company can have an impact on its (1) industrial dimensions, whereas its organizational dimensions are focused on the company itself. Environmental sustainability in the industrial sector is hindered by capital costs, competition, regulatory constraints, as well as a lack of information and technical knowledge (Murillo-Luna et al., 2011). Two limitations and organizational barriers to the implementation of green ideas were cited by Post and Altman (1994). Attitudes and behavior patterns from past practice as well as insufficient management leadership are all seen as major corporate obstacles when it comes to developing an environmental strategy in the workplace (Murillo-Luna et al., 2011).

According to the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), sustainable development is hampered by a lack of general knowledge about environmental policies and approaches, "combined with a perceived lack of information and support, which is especially prevalent in small and medium-sized enterprises" (Mitchell et al., 2020). In some cases, modern executives believe they are forced to choose between the social and environmental benefits of sustainable development and the costs of implementation, which they perceive as a trade-off between the two objectives (Deng et al., 2016). It is estimated that only a small number of hotel businesses are aware of the advantages in terms of money resulting from the implementation of environmentally friendly initiatives in their operations (Graci et al., 2008). Throughout society, there is a widespread belief that "*sustainability is expensive.*" This belief has become deeply ingrained in our collective consciousness. Sustainability leads to innovations in organizational structure and technology that have demonstrable long-term cost benefits as well as the potential to generate new revenues (Liu & Cheng, 2018). Additionally, Several factors, including the amount of time and abilities in management required to put in place a sustainability strategy, contribute to the resistance that hotel owners and operators encounter.

Finally, various studies have identified a lack of interest in sustainability as an additional barrier, as well as a lack of business relevance (Hassanli & Ashwell, 2020; Sloan et al., 2014). Shortly stated, the primary obstacles to implementing sustainability are a lack of knowledge about financial profitability over the long term, as well as a lack of accountability for environmental reporting and strategies (Guix et al., 2019). According to the authors, business practices that are environmentally and socially responsible are now either profitable or break-even in today's market, depending on the industry (Sneirson, 2019).

Research shows that, despite what many people believe, long-term cost savings and incentives for green technology investments are powerful motivators for businesses (Gan & Nuli, 2018; Sloan et al., 2014; Zientara et al., 2015). Sustainable business practices are also being adopted by corporations in an effort to capitalize on the opportunity for image improvement (Holden et al., 2017). A study conducted by Hahn and Scheermesser (2006) found that enhancing one's image is yet another motivator for people to exercise.

Another advantage of implementing sustainability in a hotel is a better competitive position in a market niche for environmentally friendly products and services (Graci & Dodds, 2008). Sustainable or responsible management decisions made by corporations can be motivated by a variety of factors, including ethical concerns, institutional pressures, or simply the "feel-good factor" (Bansal & Roth, 2000; Hahn & Scheermesser, 2006). Short-term benefits such as increased employee morale and overall job satisfaction have been realized by companies that have implemented a sustainability strategy. Motivators in their own right, these components are also considered to be (Bansal & Roth, 2000).

Online Self-Audit and Consultation Tools

Through the development, manufacturing, shipping, and use of equipment over the course of a person's lifetime, information technology contributes approximately 2% of global carbon dioxide emissions (Iannarelli & Boccaletti, 2018). The use of information technology, on the other hand, has the potential to significantly reduce carbon dioxide emissions in general (Bhatt et al., 2019). Online content can provide numerous advantages to hotels, including increased efficiency in all hotel processes (such as reservations, check-in / check-out, housekeeping, and maintenance management scheduling), among other things. Hoteliers can use some self-help online tools to audit their operations and make informed decisions as they navigate the rocky terrain of the hospitality industry.

The toolkit for implementing Hotel Energy Solutions, which was released in April of this year, is one of the more recent online resources to be made available. The HES toolkit, which was developed as a result of a collaboration between the World Tourism Organization of the United Nations, the United Nations Environment Program, the International Hotel and Restaurant Association, the French government, and the European Renewable Energy Council is now available to the general public on the internet for download. A variety of services are provided by Hotel Energy Solutions to small and medium-sized hotels, including quantifying, analyzing, and reducing their energy consumption and carbon dioxide emissions, among other things.

In order for Hotel Energy Solution and other online tools to function properly, hotels must enter specific data, such as occupancy rates, energy consumption, energy costs, and resources used. In building maintenance, as well as efforts already made to improve sustainability, must be entered into the system. With the help of the hotel's online tools, you can determine the energy efficiency and CO2 emissions of the establishments. Additional investment advice and recommendations, as well as estimated returns on investment, are provided to assist hotel managers and owners in making informed decisions. It is important to increase the efficiency of your energy use to a greater extent. Aside from that, self-reporting software accessible online serves as a benchmark for the industry as a whole.

Methodology

Email surveys and structured questionnaires were used to gather information about hotel managers' views on the barriers, motivations, as well as investment strategies. In order to mitigate environmental impacts, green technologies, as well as the potential for online self-help tools, are being explored. This research builds on the findings of a previous exploratory study.

The questionnaire development was conducted in two stages, incorporating both qualitative and quantitative research methods. First, the researchers spoke with a number of experts, including five regional managers in the Philippines, Germany, Singapore and Switzerland. Hoteliers who participated in the Hotel Energy Solutions online toolkit pilot testing were deemed knowledgeable about current issues related to self-help online tools by the Hotel Energy Solutions. They were used to gather general feedback on the questionnaire's structure, length and content from a panel of experts.

For each one of the study's five objectives, the questionnaire has five sections. First, an overview of the study's aims and the role played by the hotelier are presented. The location, size, and category of the hotel are all included in this section. After assessing hoteliers' overall attitude toward sustainability, a question was asked about the most recent investments in sustainability. The significance of five impulsive statements that were anchored by strongly disagree / strongly agree was determined using a Likert-type scale on which the responses were scored. Section three of the survey asked hoteliers about their awareness of and willingness to use self-help tools for assessing energy efficiency and mitigating environmental impacts are available online, while the fourth section of the paper discussed the factors that drive and impede sustainability investments (Hahn & Scheermesser, 2006; Hobson & Essex, 2001; Kaplan, 2008;

Nelson et al., 2021). This study's final segment focuses on online tools, asking hoteliers about their views on the future of self-help online tools and how willing they are to pay for such tools.

Email surveys were used to collect data for this study, while structured questionnaires were used to assess hotel managers' perceptions of their perceptions of online self-help tools, as well as their perceptions of barriers and motivators, were investigated. A cross-sectional study was conducted among management teams of hotels that are privately owned or operated by a chain to find out what they thought about their jobs. The email survey sampled managers from 40 hotels worldwide. The database contains hotels in four countries that meet all quality standards that must be met (e.g., resorts, AirBnb, condominiums, chains, and privately operated hotels).

Results

The collected data is represented graphically and statistically using means and frequencies. The questionnaire consisted of the following: (1) The drivers and impediments to making long-term investments in sustainability; and (2) The potential of online self-help resources.

The Drivers and Obstacles to Hoteliers Investing in Sustainability

Hotels were asked if they had made sustainability investments in the last few years to get a sense of what was motivating and discouraging them. As shown in Table 1, 21 hoteliers (52.5%) stated that they invested in energy efficiency, 14 hoteliers (35.0%) stated that they invested in waste minimization, 30 hoteliers (75.0%) stated that they invested in optimizations of processes, and 29 hoteliers (72.5%) stated that they worked on recycling strategies. A total of 31 hotel managers (or 77.5% of the total) said that hotels have made investments in environmentally friendly and sustainable architecture.

Table 1. Investment priorities (n=40)

Investment priorities	Frequency	Percentage
Energy efficiency	21	52.5%
Waste minimization	14	35.0%
Optimizations of processes	30	75.0%
Recycling strategies	29	72.5%
Sustainable architecture	31	77.5%

Other forms of investment made by hotels were made clear. There are a number of people who have been mentioned in no particular order. Some of the companies' social responsibility projects include tree planting, sewage treatment systems, organic food, soap and detergents training, geothermal energy, and a desalination plant.

During the literature review and pre-testing phases, six possible reasons for investing were identified. There was an option for participants to choose from a variety of options. In addition, the 'Others' position allowed for a full-text response to be provided. Motives that were not addressed by the answers provided. As shown in Table 2, hoteliers are primarily motivated by a desire to save money when making sustainability-related investments in their properties. There were 30 responses, or 75 percent of the hoteliers in which cost reduction was cited as a motivating factor. Seventy percent of hoteliers surveyed said that improving energy efficiency was their second most important motivation. In 57.5 percent of cases among respondents, a sense of social responsibility is a motivating factor. Twenty-two hoteliers stated that a positive increase in the overall reputation of hotels that practice sustainability was a factor in their decision to become members of the movement (55.0%). Hoteliers who want to reduce their carbon footprint consider sustainable investment to be extremely important (40.0%), while the least important comes from investors or supply chain (17.5%).

Table 2. Hoteliers' reasons for investing in sustainability (n=40)

Reasons for investing in sustainability	Frequency	Percentage
Cost reduction	30	75.0%
Energy efficiency	28	70.0%
Social responsibility	23	57.5%
Hotel's reputation	22	55.0%
Carbon footprint reduction	16	40.0%
Investors / Supply chain	7	17.5%

The following are examples of motivations with low statistical representation: a short-term competitive advantage; the customer and employee well-being is prioritized; the need for long-term equipment; the needs of clients (e.g., contract clients); "People, Planet, Profit" thinking; and taking care of the environment vs. taking care of society. In cases where multiple responses were possible, a pre-set of possible responses was used to investigate the barriers that hoteliers face when considering sustainability investments. 'Others' allows for a more detailed description of barriers that hoteliers encountered that were not on the list.

Table 3. The obstacles to hoteliers investing in sustainability (n=40)

Obstacles to hoteliers investing in sustainability	Frequency	Percentage
Lack of profitability	28	70.0%
Insufficient financial resources	26	65.0%
Complicated nature of implementation	14	35.0%
Lack of education	8	20.0%
Lack of personnel to introduce sustainability	8	20.0%
Absence of local significance	5	12.5%
Missing bus drivers	4	10.0%

Most respondents (70 percent) believe that sustainability investments will not be profitable, and a lack of financial resources is cited as the second most common obstacle by 65 percent of the total responses. About a third of those who answered the survey said that the complexity of implementing sustainability was a barrier. An insufficient supply of business drivers, staff who are competent to implement new concepts, local relevance issues for improvements in sustainability, as well as insufficient education on sustainability issues are all potential investment barriers. Respondents took advantage of the opportunity to suggest alternatives to the barriers already listed, just like they did with the motivators. Sustainability is not an issue for some hoteliers, while it is for others.

Because of this, customers do not want to pay for these additional expenditures. Owner support is lacking (e.g., the investment is deemed excessive, making short-term gains impossible); thus, there is a failure to recognize and support customers, to provide owner support, and to rely on outside experts and resources which the mentioned issues exist.

Online Self-Audit Tools' Potential

Hotels were asked in this section if they would ever use an online tool to evaluate their properties' energy efficiency. An online tool would be used by 45 percent of those polled, 30 percent said they were unsure, and 27.5 percent said they would not use an online tool at all. In order to provide more specific information about the tool they intended to use, respondents were given an additional opportunity. Hotel Power Generation Check and Hotel Energy Solutions were the two most widely used tools in the hospitality industry, according to the study. There are several software programs available that can be used to monitor the energy consumption of the Internet including ENOPLAN, Entech, Green Key, and Green Hotels Global as well as Energiecoach and Energy Contracting as well as IHG Corporate Tool, Accor Open, and LightStay/Hilton.

The energy efficiency and carbon footprint of online self-help tools are important considerations are discussed and calculations were the subject of the following question. 45 percent of respondents said they had faith in the results calculated by online tools, while 17.5 percent said they did not, and the remaining 37.5 percent said they were unsure.

When it comes to raising awareness about sustainability and evaluating a hotel's environmental performance, online self-help tools can be a useful tool. However, they can also provide additional recommendations for individual hotels. Seventy percent of the hoteliers in attendance agreed that such a tool would be useful. 22.5% of respondents were unsure of the tool's potential, while 7.5% said it would be of no use.

Respondents were asked their willingness to pay for an online tool that could help the hotel save money and reduce its carbon footprint. When asked whether they would pay for such tools, only 40% said they would; the other 60% said no. On average, hoteliers said they were willing to pay between \$800 and \$2,000 per year for the service. According to other full-text responses, spending should be proportional to the savings achieved as a result of the tool's recommendations. The sustainability of the hospitality industry, according to these critics, cannot be fully assessed solely by looking at energy efficiency.

Discussion

When it came to incorporating sustainability principles into their operations, the vast majority of hotels understood the significance of doing so. As secondary research and this exploratory study demonstrate, this has resulted in an increase in green investments in recent years. LED lighting, motion sensors that are linked to light levels, and cogeneration plants for heating are examples of this. Certain hoteliers, on the other hand, face certain limitations when it comes to implementing sustainability because they are the owners of their facilities, rather than tenants. Because they are renting the space, hotels are not allowed to make any structural changes, such as changing the roof or walls. A project's success isn't always measured in dollars, but rather in terms of what can be accomplished.

It is no secret that hotels are wary of making sustainability investments because of the potential financial losses they could incur. The hotel industry appears to be mired in a classic case of the “*money must be spent to save money*” mentality. A variety of studies have looked into the factors that might influence hoteliers' decisions about whether or not to make sustainability investments. There was a strong focus on environmental protection, cost-savings, and enhancing the company's public image. The primary drivers, according to this investigation, are a reduction in costs and an increase in energy efficiency. It is possible that the rise in hotel energy costs over the past decade has pushed the "energy efficiency" factor to the forefront of investors' minds. Hoteliers are motivated by the increased reputation that comes with implementing sustainability initiatives. It is not surprising that good behavior is rewarded by peers and customers in the face of increased public scrutiny.

The most notable obstacles to incorporating green management systems: a lack of interest, a high initial financial cost, because of a lack of information and support, and because of the overall difficulty of the implementation process (Hobson, 2021). In line with previous research on the subject, which found that an overwhelming majority of respondents stated that a lack of financial resources is the most significant impediment to sustainability investments, this finding confirms the findings of the current study. The uncertainty that hoteliers have about the long-term profitability of sustainability investments makes the barrier even more difficult to overcome. In order for hoteliers to make well-informed decisions, it appears that more information about the return on investment associated with each sustainability option is required. In a recent study, it was discovered that hoteliers enjoy using online self-help tools for evaluating the energy efficiency of their establishments.

It has been found that online self-help tools are underutilized in the hospitality industry, in particular, due to a lack of awareness about their advantages and potential applications. Those hoteliers who were already familiar with online self-help tools had all previously worked for a hotel chain that had implemented internal evaluation programs for its employees. Hoteliers are divided on the use of such instruments. Most respondents expressed an interest in the idea of using an online tool, with some of those who did not express an interest meaning they are undecided.

More information and education about technical aspects as well as the possibilities offered by online tools is needed, according to the findings. This will aid in the mitigation of environmental impacts. According to some hotels, an online tool is incapable of producing sophisticated results. Hoteliers were unable to evaluate a new online tool that they had never used before, but which aimed to assist hoteliers with complex operations such as energy efficiency, during the pre-testing phase because the tool was not available to them. According to nearly three-quarters of those who took part in the survey, online self-help tools have the potential to raise public awareness of sustainability. Hoteliers are willing to pay for an online tool that can perform an energy audit and identify benchmarking opportunities, as well as make recommendations and calculate the return on investment, because the online tool serves as consultants for them. This demonstrates, to a certain extent, that hoteliers are willing to make an investment in order to receive better advice when it comes to making investments in the area of sustainability, which is encouraging. The Hotel Energy Solutions eToolkit will be made available for free, and it is possible that the hospitality industry, which accounts for one percent of global carbon dioxide emissions, will take the lead in climate change mitigation efforts.

Conclusion

When it comes to reducing its carbon footprint, the hospitality industry possesses enormous opportunity. Workforce training and education programs, waste minimization initiatives, sustainable water schemes, and energy-efficient technologies are all things that managers have the ability to influence.

When it applied to big investment opportunities such as building systems, green technologies, and reconstruction, barriers and motivating factors play a significant role in determining final investment decisions, especially in the construction industry. The vast majority of hoteliers, on the other hand, are motivated by a desire for immediate financial gain rather than long-term viability. Businesses are increasingly realizing that aligning environmental stewardship with business strategy generates value for both the company and society as a whole.

It is necessary for hotels to have a clear picture of their current energy consumption in order for the purpose of making well-informed decisions about future investments in energy efficiency and, potentially, renewable energy sources. In this regard, online self-help tools such as the Hotel Energy Solutions can be of assistance to hoteliers. It runs a series of calculations to provide a reasonably clear picture of the building's benchmarked energy performance, which is based on current energy usage data and general information about the property and services provided by the hotel chain. Without consulting outside experts and paying their fees, it is possible for a hotelier or chief engineer to complete the initial phase of analysis without consulting or paying them. This clearly demonstrates that more information and training are required for those who were unable to name even one active online evaluation tool when questioned.

An educational campaign should be conducted by local, regional, and national hotel associations regarding energy consumption and online evaluation tools for hoteliers. Because so many people believe in the power of these tools, a system of support, such as online videos, is required. Additionally, the authors suggest a tool be created that considers environmental and social factors beyond just energy efficiency. Additionally, hoteliers must be able to learn from each other and share their knowledge, experience, and ideas by enhancing benchmarking across hotel categories and geographic locations.

As an exploratory study, there are several limitations to keep in mind. When generalizing results, the sample size has a significant impact. Owing to the fact that not every member of the targeted population had an equal chance of being chosen, the general application of non-probability samples is deemed unreliable. An extensive literature review helped to shape the questionnaire's content, which included some sources from more than a decade ago. A country's economic and/or political situation may have a significant impact on the barriers and motivations for sustainability. The online self-help tool has been a source of confusion for some hoteliers, making it difficult to analyze the questions that have been raised. Most of the questions on self-help websites are about energy efficiency and carbon footprint calculations. Thus, instead of covering a wide range of sustainability issues, such as waste reduction and water consumption, the focus is narrowed to a few key areas.

Future studies should first examine the impact of online self-help tools on the barriers and motivators that prevent hoteliers from implementing sustainability in their properties. Further research could determine the true impact of online tools on actual investments and the impact that those investments have on savings and reputation and image.

References

- Bansal, P., & Roth, K. (2000). Why companies go green: A model of ecological responsiveness. *Academy of Management Journal*, 43(4), 717-736. <https://doi.org/10.5465/1556363>
- Bhatt, P. J., Pandya, H. A., & Modi, N. R. (2019). A review of possible impacts on tourism by climate change. *Research Journal of Science, Bioinformatics, Pharmaceutical and Chemical Science*, 5(3), 93-102. <http://www.rjlbpcs.com/article-pdf-downloads/2019/28/620.pdf>
- Chen, J., Sloan, P., & Legrand, W. (2010). *Sustainability in the hospitality industry*. Routledge.
- Darnall, N., & Edwards Jr, D. (2006). Predicting the cost of environmental management system adoption: the role of capabilities, resources and ownership structure. *Strategic Management Journal*, 27(4), 301-320. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.518>
- Deng, X., Li, Z., & Gibson, J. (2016). A review on trade-off analysis of ecosystem services for sustainable land-use management. *Journal of Geographical Sciences*, 26, 953-968. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11442-016-1309-9>
- Gan, J. E., & Nuli, S. (2018). Millennials' environmental awareness, price sensitivity and willingness to pay for Green Hotels. *Journal of Tourism, Hospitality and Culinary Arts*, 10(2), 47-62. <https://ir.uitm.edu.my/id/eprint/65343/>
- Graci, S., & Dodds, R. (2008). Why go green? The business case for environmental commitment in the Canadian hotel industry. *Anatolia*, 19(2), 251-270. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13032917.2008.9687072>
- Guix, M., Font, X., & Bonilla-Priego, M. J. (2019). Materiality: Stakeholder accountability choices in hotels' sustainability reports. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 31(6), 2321-2338. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-05-2018-0366>
- Hahn, T., & Scheermesser, M. (2006). Approaches to corporate sustainability among German companies. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 13(3), 150-165.
- Hassanli, N., & Ashwell, J. (2020). The contribution of small accommodations to a sustainable tourism industry. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 23(3), 261-264. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2018.1530201>
- Hobson, K. (2021). The limits of the loops: Critical environmental politics and the Circular Economy. *Environmental Politics*, 30(1-2), 161-179. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2020.1816052>
- Hobson, K., & Essex, S. (2001). Sustainable tourism: A view from accommodation businesses. *Service Industries Journal*, 21(4), 133-146. <https://doi.org/10.1080/714005050>
- Holden, E., Linnerud, K., & Banister, D. (2017). The imperatives of sustainable development. *Sustainable Development*, 25(3), 213-226. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.1647>

- Iannarelli, G., & Boccaletti, C. (2018). Economic impact of investments in weather forecasts for distribution system operators: The Italian case. *IET Generation, Transmission & Distribution*, 12(20), 4551-4556. <https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-gtd.2017.1919>
- Kaplan, A. (2008). *Greening in the United States hotel sector: An exploratory examination* (Master's thesis, University of Nevada-Las Vegas). <https://digitalscholarship.unlv.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1610&context=thesedisertations>
- Legrand, W., Kirsche, C., Sloan, P., & Simons-Kaufmann, C. (2012). Making 20 2020 happen: Is the hospitality industry mitigating its environmental impacts? The barriers and motivators that German hoteliers have to invest in sustainable management strategies and technologies and their perceptions of online self help. *WIT Transactions on Ecology and the Environment*, 161, 115-126. <https://www.witpress.com/Secure/elibrary/papers/ST12/ST12010FU1.pdf>
- Liu, C. W., & Cheng, J. S. (2018). Exploring driving forces of innovation in the MSEs: the case of the sustainable B&B tourism industry. *Sustainability*, 10(11), 3983. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10113983>
- Mitchell, S., O'Dowd, P., & Dimache, A. (2020). Manufacturing SMEs doing it for themselves: Developing, testing and piloting an online sustainability and eco-innovation toolkit for SMEs. *International Journal of Sustainable Engineering*, 13(3), 159-170. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19397038.2019.1685609>
- Murillo-Luna, J. L., Garcés-Ayerbe, C., & Rivera-Torres, P. (2011). Barriers to the adoption of proactive environmental strategies. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 19(13), 1417-1425. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2011.05.005>
- Nelson, K. M., Partelow, S., Stäbler, M., Graci, S., & Fujitani, M. (2021). Tourist willingness to pay for local green hotel certification. *Plos One*, 16(2), e0245953. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0245953>
- Post, J. E., & Altma, B. W. (1994). Managing the environmental change process: barriers and opportunities. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 7(4), 64-81. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09534819410061388>
- Pratt, L., Rivera, L., Bien, A., & Peeters, PM. (2011). Tourism: investing in energy and resource efficiency. In S. Fulai, & P. Sukhdev (Eds.), *Towards a green economy: pathways to sustainable development and poverty eradication* (pp. 413-451). UNEP.
- Sloan, P., Legrand, W., & Simons-Kaufmann, C. (2014). A survey of social entrepreneurial community-based hospitality and tourism initiatives in developing economies: A new business approach for industry. *Worldwide Hospitality and Tourism Themes*, 6(1), 51-61. <https://doi.org/10.1108/WHATT-11-2013-0045>
- Sneirson, J. F. (2019). The history of shareholder primacy, from Adam Smith through the rise of financialism. In B. Sjøfjell & C. M. Bruner (Eds.), *Cambridge handbook of corporate law, corporate governance and sustainability*. Cambridge University Press. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3383405
- Zientara, P., Kujawski, L., & Bohdanowicz-Godfrey, P. (2015). Corporate social responsibility and employee attitudes: Evidence from a study of Polish hotel employees. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 23(6), 859-880. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2015.1019511>